

Study of magnetic dipole moment of the pulsars

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Abstract

Pulsars are the ideal object to study the physics of matter under extreme conditions. Magnetic properties are crucial to understand the exterior and interior environment of the pulsars. Magnetosphere of the neutron star emits magnetic dipole radiation. We introduce the electrodynamic approach of intensity within a length domain and to setup a relationship between magnitude of star and magnetic dipole moment. The present study is based on the radioflux at a distance of 10 parsec of the variable star.

1. Introduction

Neutron stars are the compact objects having variable densities at different radius scales. Categorically density of the core is 10^{15} g/cm^3 in a spherical symmetry of more neutron presence. Neutron stars could potentially be an ideal environment to study the physics parameters in an extreme conditions. In the material Universe which is still in a question of how the internal structure of the star is changing in regard to time, temperature and internal energy. Overcome study of (Oppenheimer and Volkoff, 1939) explained the mass-radius relationship of neutron stars through the mass of neutron stars. Primarily the degeneracy is not uniform throughout the neutron star. On the other hand, interaction among neutrons due to short range forces will make a neutron star more compact. In spite of this, mutually interacting neutrons give rise to equation of state and curve of growth, which is denoted by polytropic index.

The internal properties of the internal mode of the neutron star can be studied through (Christensen-Dalsgaard and Thompson, 2010) in which eigenvalues of the neutron star can be precisely estimated. Pulsars radiation comes from the rotating neutron star. The interval of the pulsar radiation varies between millisecond to second.

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2. Magnetic dipole moment of pulsar

In neutron star (Pacini, 1967, 1968; Bertotti, 1969; Ostriker and Gunn, 1969) which described the emission process of pulsar by using the rotational kinetic energy of the rotating neutron star. In a simplest configuration of the rotating neutron star, the emanation of the magnetic dipole moment (\vec{m}) of pulsars at time t is given by,

$$\vec{m}(t) = \frac{B_p R_{NS}^3}{2} (\vec{e}_\perp \sin \alpha \cos \Omega t + \vec{e}'_\perp \sin \alpha \sin \Omega t + \vec{e}_\parallel \cos \alpha) \quad (1)$$

Where $\vec{e}_\perp, \vec{e}'_\perp, \vec{e}_\parallel$ are unit vectors, B_p is the magnetic field strength at the magnetic pole, R_{NS} is the radius of the of the neutron star. Whereas α is the angle to the rotation axis, Ω is the angular velocity of the neutron star. The equation 1 shows the magnetic moment of rotating neutron star. The rate of change of magnetic moment is given by,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{m}(t) = \frac{B_p R_{NS}^3 \Omega}{2} (\vec{e}'_\perp \sin \alpha \cos \Omega t - \vec{e}_\perp \sin \alpha \sin \Omega t) \quad (2)$$

We studied the following cases:

(i) At pole of the neutron star, $\alpha = 0$:

$$|m| = \frac{B_p R_{NS}^3}{2} \quad (3)$$

(ii) Non-rotating neutron star $\Omega = 0$:

$$\vec{m}(t) = \frac{B_p R_{NS}^3}{2} (\vec{e}_\perp \sin \alpha + \vec{e}_\parallel \cos \alpha) \implies \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{m}(t) = 0 \quad (4)$$

The relation 4 shows the existence of magnetic moment of non-rotating neutron star but no change in magnetic moment. According to the neutron star mass-radius relation, R_{NS} (Shapiro and Teukolsky, 2008) can be expressed as,

$$R_{NS} = \frac{15.12}{(M/M_\odot)^{1/3}} \text{ km} \quad (5)$$

Substituting equation 5 in 3 gives,

$$|m| = \frac{B_p}{2} \frac{3.456 \times 10^{21}}{(M/M_\odot)} \text{ Gauss-cm}^3 \quad (6)$$

The relation 6 shows the dependency of magnetic moment (at pole) on mass of the neutron star. This implies, larger magnetic moment occurs on the smaller values of the neutron star mass. This affects the pulsar emission mechanism.

3. Luminosity of pulsars

Luminosity is the energy emitted per second per unit cross-sectional area by the star is the important physical parameter for the pulsar. In reference to Australia Telescope National Facility Catalogue (Manchester et al., 2005) at the wave band of 1400 MHz, the total radio luminosity (L) of the pulsar is given the expression (Lorimer and Kramer, 2004; Wu et al., 2020):

$$L = \frac{4\pi d^2}{\delta} \sin^2\left(\frac{\rho}{2}\right) \int_{\nu_{\min}}^{\nu_{\max}} S_{\text{mean}}(\nu) d(\nu) \quad (7)$$

where δ is pulsar duty cycle (≈ 0.04), ρ is emission angle of pulsar ($\approx 6^\circ$), d is the distance of pulsar, ν_{\min} is the lower limit of frequency (≈ 10 MHz) and ν_{\max} is the upper limit of frequency (≈ 100 GHz) for pulsar observation. $S_{\text{mean}}(\nu)$ is mean flux density observed at a given ν . S_{1400} is mean flux density at 1400 MHz (mJy), substituting above numerical value in the equation 7, expression of luminosity becomes :

$$L \approx 7.4 \times 10^{27} \frac{\text{erg}}{\text{s}} \left(\frac{S_{1400}}{\text{mJy}}\right) \left(\frac{d}{\text{kpc}}\right)^2 \quad (8)$$

For pulsar PSR B0540-69 in the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC), mean flux density S_{1400} is 24 μJy (Johnston and Romani, 2003; Johnston et al., 2004) at a distance of 10 parsec, the luminosity;

$$L \approx 1.776 \times 10^{20} \text{erg.s}^{-1} \quad (9)$$

This represents the absolute luminosity of the pulsar PSR B0540-69.

4. Polytropes of neutron star

Polytropic index plays the crucial role in the internal structure neutron star, which in turn affects the pulsar emission mechanism. The dependency of the ratio of potential energy of the polytrope (ξ) and potential energy of the neutron star (GM^2R^{-1}) on polytropic index (n) as shown in figure 1. The description of various polytropes inside the star as shown in table 1.

5. Summary

Pulsar exhibits many challenging astrophysical processes, which are still difficult to observe precisely. This work gives an introductory overview of the magnetic dipole behaviour of the pulsar, polytropic indices of the neutron star, including the luminosity of the pulsar at a 10 parsec.

Figure 1: Ratio of the potential energy of the polytrope with the potential energy of star as function of the polytropic index

n	- ξ/GM^2R^{-1}	Stages as a function of time
0 – 1.4	0.600 – 0.833	uniform density
1.5 – 2.9	0.857 – 1.429	convective equilibrium non-relativistic degeneracy
3.0 – 3.4	1.500 – 1.875	standard model relativistic degeneracy
3.5 – 4.9	2.000 – 30.000	relativistic degeneracy
5.0	∞	complete central condensation
∞	∞	isothermal configuration

Table 1: Characteristic of some polytrope, (Abhyankar, 2001)

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Data Availability Statement

No data is generated in this article.

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